

Just a simple Engineering Structure ...

Rehabilitation of a vapor discharge tower

Henrichshütte Iron Works, Hattingen / Ruhr (Germany)

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Preview

1. Introduction: the site
2. The challenge (casting machine and tower)
3. Samples for damages
4. Decision making and planning
5. Construction work
6. Ongoing projects

The former Henrichshütte Blast Furnace Work

A pig casting machine at work

Samples of the challenges for conservation work

Inspection

Bild A3.33: Knoten der vorderen rechten Schräge mit Eckpfosten 2 in Ebene 2

Inspection

Bild A3.22: Knoten von vordem Querriegel und Mittelpfosten in Ebene 4 oben

Building survey

Bild 2: Darstellung der Bauwerksteile des Schwadenturms mit Hauptebenen, Nummerierung der Stützen und Ebene der Maschinenbühne (blau)

Decision making

The vapor discharge tower:

- Removal of the old panels inevitable
- Unique chance to rehabilitate the structure

Decision making

The machinery platform:

- Bad steel quality, heavy corrosion
- Danger of sudden breakdown
- Need for strengthening the structure
- Repair of damaged girders instead of substitution
- Adaptive load bearing support structure

Procedure (Action Planning)

1. Enclosure of the construction site
2. Cleaning up and waste disposal of the hazardous Eternit panels (asbestos!) from the platform
3. Scaffolding and encasement of the tower
4. Dismantling and waste disposal of the resting Eternit panels according to special technical rules, inspection and repair / renewal of the mounting supports for the panels
5. Steel construction works at the tower
6. Corrosion treatment (grit blasting and new coating)
7. Installation of new panels (asbestos free)
8. Engine platform: installation of a working platform below the machine platform, dismantling of the bar grates, cleaning up, rehabilitation of the steel structure, adaptive load bearing structure, corrosion protection, re-installation of bar grates
9. Cleaning up and vacation of the construction site
10. Restoration work on the pig casting machinery

Steel structure repair

Steel structure repair

Corrosion protection

**View into the
tower with new
panels**

Heavy corrosion of the machine platform

Heavy corrosion of the machine platform

Heavy corrosion

Heavy corrosion

Rehabilitation of the
steel structure

Rehabilitation of the steel structure

Rehabilitation of the steel structure

Column base before
and after corrosion
treatment

Corrosion protection (a former repair measurement)

Prinzipdarstellung Unterstützung Maschinenbühne

- Erläuterungen:**
- 10 Trägernummer alt
 - S1 Stützennummer alt
 - UT 1 Trägernummer neu
 - ST 1 Stützennummer neu
 - KS 1 Kurze Stützen neu

- Ebene 4: 4.80m bis 5.10m
- Ebene 3: 4.50m bis 4.80m
- Ebene 5: 4.20m bis 4.50m
- Ebene 1: 3.90m bis 4.20m
- Ebene 0: 3.60m bis 3.90m

Alle Maße sind ca-Wert gemäß örtlichem Aufmaß

Name	Datum	Art der Änderung	Index
Ingenieurbüro für Bautechnik Prof. Dr.-Ing. R. Harnach		Herner Str. 141 44809 Bochum Telefon: 0234/95123-0 Telefax: 0234/95123-19	
Bauherr	Landschaftsverband Westfalen-Lippe		
Bauwerk	13.2: Masselanlage Förderband		
Bauwerksteil	13.2.1: Maschinenbühne		
42,0 x 29,7 Blattgr.:	C.L. Gez.:	27.02.03 Datum:	1:50 Maßstab: Blatt-Nr.:

Draufsicht Stützen und Fundamente

Schnitt 3-3

Engine platform – adaptive load bearing structure

Schnitt A-A

Engine platform – adaptive load bearing structure

Adaptive load bearing structure

Color scheme:

Vapor discharge tower: GREEN

Machine platform: DARK GREY old structure / LIGHT GREY new adaptive structure

Transformation of a „simple“ engineering structure

Engine platform – „under construction“

Engine platform – „under construction“

Engine platform – construction work completed ...

Ongoing Projects

- Pig casting plant: building survey and rehabilitation of the casting house, the structure of the conveyor belts and auxiliary installations
- Pig casting machine: preservation treatment of the conveyor belt with pig molds, including the driving engines
- Maintenance planning

Casting machine
conveyor belt structure

Ongoing projects

(rust never
sleeps ...)

Iron tapping platform

**Thank You
for Your
Attention !**

